

Associability of Corporate Ethics with Yamas and Niyamas of Patanjali's Yoga Sutras

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Abstract:

Relevance- In times of cut throat competition in corporates, personal and professional challenges have increased by many times. There has been an increase in cases of dishonesty, corruption, work dis-satisfaction, sexual exploitation and disrespect for colleagues at work place. The holistic approach of Indian Wisdom is needed for modern management to integrate work with its essence and professional skills with values. Value-based holistic approach to management will ensure such all-round wholesome human development and prosperity. In this review article, Patanjali's Yoga sutras are evaluated for their practical relevance in today's competitive corporate world.

Aims and objectives The single pointed objective of this research is to evaluate the associability of yamas and Niyamas from yog sutras, with modern corporate ethics.

Methodology- The methodology of this work is a theoretical review of classical yogic text 'Yog Sutra', and modern texts of corporate ethics.

Major Findings A management with proper combination of values and skills can assure harmony and progress of organisation as well as society. The 5 Yamas and the 5 Niyamas, mentioned in Yoga Sutras, are not only the starting grounds for yogic sadhna but also co-relate with the professional ethics needed to succeed in a long term business. Individual ethics like leadership, honesty, trust, loyalty etc., are found to be strongly co-related with the yamas and niyamas of Maharshi Patanjali. Further these ethical assets can be inculcated in corporate employees through practice of yoga. This review revisits balance between profit making business skills and ethics embedded in yogic wisdom.

Keywords- Yama, Niyama, Corporate Ethics, Work-Life Balance, Business Ethics.

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Introduction

Online work culture in today's world, requires virtual presence of employees. As a result, many employees have started 'moonlighting', which means working for more than one employer at a time. This is not only illegal but also unethical because a person can be working for two competitive companies at the same time and selling confidential data. As a head of corporate also, individuals must prioritise employee interests along with company profits. But today we see many cases of employee harassment, labour exploitation and insecure minded management mindsets.

The present times are witnessing as many negative news in work culture and business ethics as many opportunities of positive nature known. This is a result of lack of wisdom and morality individually, as well as at the level of society. Our individual egos also have become rigid so as to not allow any moral policing from any external interference. In this scenario, work ethics and values have become rarer and much in demand and there is an immediate need of realising the potential of wisdom lying in the yogic philosophies of Yamas and Niyamas, to meet these demands. These philosophies are time tested and have been a subject of study by social engineers, researchers and philanthropists.

The need to understand these ethical behaviours highlights the importance of the principles underlying these desired ethical behaviours. Also it becomes necessary to identify principles contributing to unethical behaviours from people who are otherwise good and talented (Alexandra et.al., 2022). Applying moral philosophy however, to business ethics is no simple task, especially in the global marketplace where notions of right and wrong mean different things for different cultures (Lewis, 2023). The Yoga Sutras of Maharshi Patanjali offer 196 "threads" of wisdom and provide guidelines for living a more meaningful and purposeful life.

These ten commandments in Yamas and Niyamas are universally applicable and relevant. A psychological method to overcome the desire for inappropriate action is recommended; this consists of training the mind to revert back to the commitment through "contrary thought" process. In other words, if a desire arises to tell say, a falsehood, we think of the long-term consequence of such an action, and stick to truth even if it brings short-term discomfort. This method of "contrary thinking (pratiprasava)" is useful till we are well established in yama and niyama (Srinivasan TM, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

The present study aims to examine and interpret the significance of Indian philosophical traditions, with particular emphasis on the Yoga Sutras, in the domain of corporate ethics. This work represents a sincere effort to identify how ethical principles embedded within classical yogic literature can be meaningfully applied to contemporary business practices and frameworks of corporate governance. To evaluate the associability of yamas and Niyamas from yog sutras, with modern corporate ethics.

Legal but not ethical

- There are legalities and laws that govern the corporates then why is there a need to have ethics?
- If corporate ethics are important then why can't laws be made according to them?

The answer to first question is quite simple. Overpricing the goods that are in demand, and lowering the quantity/quality of a product while in high demand, is not illegal but is not ethical as well. There may be instances where the product advertises a different asset in a said product, prints something else in the list of ingredients and the overall experience of consumer is entirely different. These instances may not be illegal but they certainly are manipulations of a certain kind.

The second question has its answer in the fact that ethics are a subject of trained mind and self-imposed boundaries for achieving bliss and prosperity. It cannot be monitored by external factors, or if tried, it may lead to manipulation. Hence the ethics behind these practices may be questionable.

Why are Business Ethics Important?

Ethics in business are important to frame as compulsory because of following reasons

- Brand recognition and growth
- Increased ability to negotiate
- Increased trust in products and services
- Customer retention and growth

- Attracts talent
- Attracts investors

Yamas and Niyamas

Maharishi Patanjali, sage scientist and one of the greatest philosophers of yoga, very precisely details on Yamas (Ahimsa, Satya, Asteya, Brahmacharya and Aparigraha) and Niyamas (Saucha, Santosha, Tapa, Swadhyay and Ishwarpranidhan)⁹ and encourages each individual to reflect on their thinking and behavioural grounds before jumping into Asanas and other practices.

Late YogGuru B K S Iyengar describes both the *Yamas* and *Niyamas* as the ‘golden keys to unlock the spiritual gates’, as they transform each action into one that originates from a deeper and more ‘connected’ place within ourselves. From that state of being, we move closer towards wholeness, connectedness and unity, and start to not just ‘do’ yoga, but live and breathe ‘yoga’ in each and every moment. Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, the world renowned Spiritual Guru, says, “Yoga has eight limbs, like a chair which has got four legs. Each one is connected to the whole. If you pull one leg, the whole chair comes.

The Yamas primarily focus on our actions when in community with others, while the Niyamas focus more generally on our relationship with our own physical and psychological selves. That says the fact why Yamas are also called Mahavrat. The Niyamas are Personal observances that concentrate on our attitudes and behaviours toward and within ourselves and also provide us with the self-discipline and inner strength we need to advance down the road to complete enlightenment, inner peace, and satisfaction.

Our mind has multiple layers of samskars accumulated over a period of years and experiences in various various births. These sanskaras manifest in the form of Smriti (memory) among the other **Pancha Vrittis** Pramana (right knowledge) Viparyaya (misconception) Vikalpa (imagination or feeling) Nidra (deep sleep). Also there are **Pancha Kleshas** or ‘five obstacles,⁹⁹ afflictions in the mind which form the root causes of all suffering. The pancha klesha are: Avidya (ignorance), Asmita (egoism), Raga (craving), Dvesha (aversion), Abhinivesha (clinging to life). Then there are layers of gross body and subtle body explained by Maharshi Patanjali as **Pancha koshas**. Annamaya kosha (the food sheath) Pranamaya kosha (the sheath of vital life force energy) Manomaya kosha (the mental or psychological sheath) Vijnanamaya kosha (the intellect sheath) Anandamaya kosha (the bliss sheath) are the panchkoshas, which are five layers of awareness through which all experience is filtered

This entire complex set up, which is still beyond the reach of gross scientific studies of today’s modern world, is way too unmanageable for ordinary people. These Yamas and Niyamas are a set of code of right conduct and are solution provided by the sage for directing these Vrittis, checking the Kleshas and nourishing/curing the Koshas. The practice of Yamas and Niyamas thus, has a deep impact in purification process of **mind**, which is the root cause of all misery if not guided by soul. This is the main reason why Maharshi Patanjali’s yoga Sutras are also known as **Indian book of Psychology** as there are clear roadmaps for mapping the mind (psyche).

The corporate scenario also works as per human Psyche. If the mind is pure every product will be consciously created to serve humans and therefore the goal of money making is replaced by a conscious choice of “**Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah**”. If every person is committed to deliver their best, then problems like frauds, corruption, pollution (industry generated), sexual harassments, financial crimes and social crimes might be things of past!

How often do we wonder, why the electronics companies who give guarantee/warranty of their products seriously pursue their customers’ interest besides loss? Why big corporates immediately accept returns of big appliances also if any manufacturing defect is detected? Why there is no questions asked return policy on online shopping apps and a whole logistics business is flourishing during the whole process of ordering and returning goods? This is more than just marketing strategy; this is their company’s ethics. No doubt the ethics are put in place keeping long term benefits in mind, still every corporate works on the subtle sense of pride embedded in the minds of its employees.

Methodology

In this review, theoretical analysis is done based on yoga sutra and contemporary texts on corporate ethics.

Discussion

The Values relevant to work ethics or corporate ethics to be specific, such as nishtha (sincerity), samarpana (commitment), kartavya-parayanta (responsibility), aparigraha (non-possession), brahmacharya (moral conduct), jigyasa (curiosity to learn), kauslam (efficiency), vividha (innovation), samatva (impartiality), etc. are defined very well in Patanjali Yoga Sutras. Indian culture is based on cherished values of satyam (truth), shivam (righteousness) and sundaram (beauty) (Chandrani Chattopadhyay, 2012).

The Maggi controversy of 2015 serves as a significant illustration of how ethical lapses can severely impact corporate credibility. The issue emerged when a state laboratory in Gorakhpur and the Central Food Laboratory in Kolkata reported the presence of monosodium glutamate (MSG) in Maggi noodle samples. Nestlé India, however, maintained that MSG was not added to Maggi products sold in the Indian market. Subsequently, the matter escalated when legal action was initiated by the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC), and the Supreme Court took cognizance of allegations regarding excessive lead content in the popular food product. Lead, being a hazardous heavy metal, accumulates in the human body and poses serious health risks, particularly to children. According to the World Health Organization, even minimal exposure to lead can have neurotoxic effects, raising grave concerns when such substances are present in products consumed on a daily basis.

In the aftermath of this crisis, Nestlé India's challenge extended beyond regaining market share; it involved rebuilding trust, especially among its own employees. Employees act as the first stakeholders and consumers of business-to-consumer products, making their confidence in the company's ethical standards critical. Restoring internal trust therefore requires a renewed commitment to corporate responsibility and ethical practices. This case is not an isolated incident but reflects a broader pattern where profit motives have overshadowed ethical considerations. Corporate ethical breakdowns have become increasingly frequent and costly, often stemming from systemic organizational issues rather than isolated individual decisions.

Another example we can take is of TATA products. The kind of reputation that late Shri Ratan Tata had earned over the years is because of the ethics that company held. Also the employee centric policies have inspired other industrialists to prioritise on maintaining a positive work environment.

According to the review of Ron Carucci, there are 4 reasons why these failures happen and why even generally good people end up in such corruption-

- a) It is psychologically unsafe to speak up
- b) There is excessive pressure to reach unrealistic performance targets
- c) Conflicting goals provoke a sense of unfairness.
- d) A positive example isn't being set.

Here comes in picture Indian system of ethics that is deeply embedded in moral and social code of India. We have visited each and every yama and niyama mentioned in Patanjali yoga Sutra. Apparently, mere study of these Niyamas however, cannot change anything. Constant efforts to practice these Indian ethics every moment of life is very important. Change can happen when not only individually, but at a mass level of society we practice these Yamas and Niyamas. Our mental processes, behaviours, choices, interpersonal relationships, daily habits, and even the environments we engage with collectively demonstrate the depth to which yoga is integrated into our lives (Shah, 2020).

The general business ethics principles and their correlation with yama-niyamas:

Ethics	Yamas	Niyamas
i. Leadership and Accountability	Asteya	Tapa
ii. Integrity	Satya	Swadhyay, Santosh
iii. Respect for others	Ahimsa Brahmcharya	Shauch
iv. Honesty	Satya	Tapas
v. Respect for laws		Ishwarpranidhan Swadhyay
vi. Responsibility	Aparigrah	Tapas
vii. Transparency	Satya	
viii. Compassion	Ahimsa	
ix. Fairness		Santosh
x. Loyalty		Ishwarpranidhan
xi. Objectivity		Tapas
xii. Environmental concern,	Aparigrah	Ishwarpranidhan Santosh
xiii. Trustworthiness	Satya, Asteya	
xiv. Professional Competence and Due Care	Asteya	Swadhya
xv. Professional Behaviour	Brahmcharya	Saucha, Santosh
xvi. Technological Practices and Ethics		Swadhya

xvii. Confidentiality	Satya	Saucha
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Conclusions

1. Yamas and Niyamas are a way to purify ourselves internally and externally to make our life more susceptible and absorbing for good things around.
2. Yamas and Niyamas are also a code of conduct, which are universally applicable and do not clash with each other's. Just like a person's dharma needs to be followed without hesitation as per Bhagwad geeta, Yamas and Niyamas also need consistency and effort and should be followed at all times with everyone.
3. Every yama and niyama corresponds to spiritual, social, commercial and service related ethics which is demanded in today's world of business and corporate.
4. Only writing books and circulars on ethics in a corporate will not help in cultivation of ethics. A constant practice of yoga in office along with talking about the yamas and Niyamas by yoga teacher might take the corporate ahead.
5. There is a need to elaborate and motivate good examples in and around, and constantly endorse people who are successfully practicing ethics within the business or outside in society.
6. As individuals, it is important for the employees to introspect and cultivate these virtues inside them.
7. There should be sessions every fortnight or month to boost internal growth just as we chase materialistic targets of the business.
8. In the government corporates these ideas should be more strongly implemented so as to put an example for private corporates.
9. Government policies should abide by these ethics so as to conserve, motivate and protect the people following and practicing ethics.

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